

ON THE DELAMINATION BEHAVIOUR OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTICS UNDER MIXED-MODE FATIGUE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Delamination under Mixed-Mode I/II fatigue loading is studied in a graphite/epoxy and a graphite/PEEK composite. Five load cases are considered: Pure mode I loading, pure mode II loading and 3 Mixed-Mode I/II cases. The DCB, ENF and the MMB (Mixed-Mode-Bending) test methods are used to obtain the desired loading. Sinusoidal loading at a displacement ratio of $R = 0.1$ and a frequency of $f = 5$ Hz is applied and crack initiation curves (S-N curves) are determined according to an initiation criterion based on an increment of crack growth of 0.3 mm. The results show that under fatigue the mode II loading becomes critical for the tougher matrix.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon-fibre polymer composites are suitable aerospace materials because of their high specific stiffness and strength. The inherent heterogeneity and anisotropy lead to a rather complex failure behaviour of composite laminates. Delamination, the debonding of adjacent plies is a commonly observed failure mode in laminates that is mainly due to a mismatch in elastic constants between plies of different fibre orientation. For instance low velocity impact and interlaminar stress concentrations at structural discontinuities can lead to the formation of delaminations. Since the occurrence of delaminations cannot be ruled out and since they sometimes are quite difficult to detect a sound knowledge of the initiation and propagation behaviour of delaminations is important to evaluate the damage tolerance of composites.

Linear-elastic fracture mechanics is a good tool to characterise delaminations. An arbitrary crack tip loading can be separated in three fracture modes: the opening mode (mode I), forward shear (mode II) and transverse shear (mode III). In a realistic component that contains a delamination the loading at the delamination front consists of a combination of all three loading modes. Adequate mode III testing has only recently become available and therefore mode III is not considered in this study.

To characterise the delamination behaviour under variable loading quasistatic and fatigue experiments under pure mode I, pure mode II and Mixed-Mode I/II loading were conducted. In particular the influence of the fracture mode on the delamination under static and fatigue loading and the influence of matrix toughness on the fatigue performance was studied. The complete characterisation over the entire mode I/II range could be used as a database for damage modelling and as a tool to assess whether defects (e.g. found during inspections) threaten the safety of components.

MATERIALS AND TEST SPECIMENS

Two materials were studied: Ciba/Geigy's HTA/6376, a carbon fibre (CF) reinforced toughened epoxy (a so called second generation epoxy) and ICI's AS4/APC2, a CF reinforced thermoplast (Poly-Ether-Ether-Keton; PEEK). HTA/6376 is one of the materials used by Airbus in recent designs of composite components. Its curing temperature is 170 °C. AS4/APC2 exhibits a superior interlaminar fracture toughness due to the very high toughness of PEEK. The high melting temperature of 350 °C causes manufacturing problems which is one of the reasons why only few components made of APC2 are in use up to now .

All experiments were performed on the same type of specimen: a 24 ply laminate with unidirectional fibre orientation. The typical ply thickness was about 0.125 mm resulting in a specimen thickness of about 3 mm. The specimens were between 24 and 26 mm wide and about 150 mm long. A thin starter film was inserted between plies 12 and 13 (i.e. in the mid-plane) at one end of each specimen during the lay-up of the prepreg. A 12 µm PFA film was used for the epoxy laminates and a slightly thicker but temperature resistant Kapton film for the PEEK. All specimens were manufactured at Daimler-Benz Aerospace Airbus in Bremen / Germany.

The thickness of the starter film causes a resin rich area to form just ahead of the film. Precracking prior to the actual test has been done in many previous works. However, precracking can lead to R-curve effects resulting in artificially high values of fracture toughness. In accordance with recent testing recommendations [1, 2] all experiments were conducted without precracking, i.e. directly from the insert.

The preparation of the specimens consisted of the following steps: measurement of the dimensions, C-scan (random samples), measurement of flexural stiffness in a 3-point bending rig (uncracked part only) and coating of the edges with a brittle white paint (type writer correction fluid). All experiments were performed at room temperature and in uncontrolled humidity.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) test is the standard test method for mode I testing of interlaminar fracture properties of composite laminates [1, 2]. A rectangular beam (as described above) is subjected to crack opening load through load hinges or end blocks bonded to the specimen. During testing the load P and the crack opening displacement COD are recorded. In addition the crack length a is measured optically with a travelling microscope on one side of the specimen. The experiment is usually analysed with the Berry method, in which the measured compliance $C = \text{COD}/P$ is plotted vs. the crack length a in a log-log diagram. A straight line is fitted to the data. The slope n of this curve (according to $C = a^n / \text{const.}$) is then used to calculate the Strain Energy Release Rate (SERR) at the crack tip [3] as

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{dC}{da} = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{n a^{n-1}}{\text{const.}} = \frac{n P^2 C}{2 b a} = \frac{n \text{ COD } P}{2 b a} \quad (1)$$

where b is the specimen width. Note that problems associated with determining beam thickness and Young's modulus are avoided in this representation.

The most commonly used method for mode II (forward shear) testing is the End Notched Flexure (ENF) test [2, 4]. The ENF test is essentially a 3-point bending test, where the specimen (as described above) is placed in the fixture such that the crack tip lies roughly between one support and the loading pin. The shear loading and the tensile and compressive loading above respectively below the delamination result in a pure mode II loading at the crack tip [4]. During testing the applied load P , the beam deflection at the loading pin and the crack length a (by travelling microscope) are measured. A span width of $2L = 100$ mm is used. The compliance of the ENF

specimen can be calculated according to simple Beam Theory (BT) as

$$C = \frac{2L^3 + 3a^3}{96EI} = \frac{2L^3 + 3a^3}{8Ebh^3} \quad (2)$$

b is the specimen width, h half the beam thickness, E the Young's modulus and $I = bh^3/12$.

It has been described earlier that the flexural stiffness of the specimens was determined in a 3-point bending set-up. Eqn (2) yields with $a = 0$ as the uncracked specimens compliance

$$C_0 = \frac{2L^3}{96EI} \quad (3)$$

For all ENF fatigue experiments an experimental compliance calibration was conducted in which the relation

$$\frac{C}{C_0} = B_0 + \frac{3}{2} B_1 \left(\frac{a}{L}\right)^3 \quad (4)$$

was fitted to the measured data for compliance C and crack length a by linear regression. The SERR in mode II is calculated using Eqn (4) as

$$G_{II} = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{dC}{da} = \frac{9C_0 B_1 a^2 P^2}{4bL^3} \quad (5)$$

Figure 1: Mixed-Mode-Bending (MMB) test

The Mixed-Mode-Bending (MMB) test after Reeder and Crews [5, 6] was used for testing under Mixed-Mode I/II loading. The MMB test is essentially a combination of DCB and ENF test. As indicated in Figure 1 the specimen is subjected simultaneously to global bending (mode II) and crack opening loading (mode I) with a lever. The loading position c on the lever determines the relative magnitudes of the mode I and mode II components. The Mixed-Mode ratio (defined as $g_{12} = G_I / G_{II}$) can be adjusted over a wide range. The load is applied over a saddle and a roller thereby reducing geometric non-linearities and allowing vertical loading only [6]. The main advantage of the MMB test set-up over other Mixed-Mode I/II testing methods are the facts that the Mixed-Mode ratio is virtually constant as the crack advances and that testing at all Mixed-Mode

ratios is conducted on the same simple type of specimen (thus avoiding comparability issues). During testing the load P_a on the lever and the displacement δ of the loading roller are recorded as well as the crack length a .

According to Williams [7] the components G_I and G_{II} of the SERR can be determined from the local moments on the crack tip. These moments are found by solving the equilibrium equations for the lever and the specimen. The following expressions were derived in [6]

$$G_I = \frac{3 a^2 P_a^2 (3c-L)^2}{4 b^2 h^3 L^2 E_{11}} \cdot \alpha \quad \text{with } \alpha = \left(1 + \frac{2}{\lambda a} + \frac{1}{(\lambda a)^2} + \frac{1}{10} \left(\frac{h}{a} \right)^2 \frac{E_{11}}{G_{13}} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{and } G_{II} = \frac{9 a^2 P_a^2 (c+L)^2}{16 b^2 h^3 L^2 E_{11}} \cdot \beta \quad \text{with } \beta = \left(1 + \frac{1}{5} \left(\frac{h}{a} \right)^2 \frac{E_{11}}{G_{13}} \right) \quad (7)$$

where a is the crack length, b the specimen width, h half the specimen thickness, $2L$ the span width, E_{11} Young's modulus in the longitudinal direction and G_{13} the shear modulus. λ is an anisotropy parameter defined as $\lambda = 1/h \cdot \sqrt[4]{6 E_{22}/E_{11}}$. α and β are correction terms to accommodate shear deformation and elastic foundation effects. The Mixed-Mode ratio is a function of the loading position c and can be calculated with Eqns (6) and (7) as

$$g_{12} = \frac{G_I}{G_{II}} = \frac{4}{3} \cdot \left(\frac{3c-L}{c+L} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{\alpha}{\beta} \quad (8)$$

Due to the weight of the upper section of the MMB apparatus (≈ 6.5 N) a small load on the specimen is present that is not accounted for in Eqns (6) and (7). Especially for fatigue experiments at low load levels the errors in calculation of the SERR can exceed 10% and should therefore not be neglected. Correction factors for the apparatus used in this study were derived in [8]. The SERR under the external load P_a and the weight of the fixture are calculated (using C_0 from Eqn (3) and $I = bh^3/12$, where the span width in the 3-point bending experiment is the same as the one in the MMB test) as

$$G_I = \frac{48 a^2 C_0}{b L^3} \cdot \left(\frac{3c-L}{4L} P_a + 1.095N \cdot \frac{c}{L} + 2.31N \cdot \frac{86.0\text{mm}}{L} - 4.63 N \right)^2 \cdot \alpha \quad (9)$$

$$\text{and } G_{II} = \frac{36 a^2 C_0}{b L^3} \cdot \left(\frac{c+L}{4L} P_a + 0.365N \cdot \frac{c}{L} + 0.77N \cdot \frac{86.0\text{mm}}{L} + 0.57 N \right)^2 \cdot \beta \quad (10)$$

As elaborated below, an analytical relation for the compliance of the MMB specimen as a function of crack length a and loading position c is a valuable tool for the analysis of fatigue experiments. Such a relation was derived in [8] based on simple beam theory assuming a rigid lever and small rotations. The compliance function $C = C(a, c)$ was found to be

$$C(a, c) = \frac{a^3 \left(39 \left(\frac{c}{L} \right)^2 - 18 \frac{c}{L} + 7 \right) + 2L^3 \left(1 + \frac{c}{L} \right)^2}{96 E_{11} I} \quad (11)$$

Eqn (11) can be used for simple calculations on the stability of crack growth. Crack growth is stable if the energy available for crack advancement decreases as the crack grows, i.e. $dG/da < 0$. In displacement control the total SERR ($G_{Tot} = G_I + G_{II}$) can be expressed as

$$G_{Tot} = \frac{P^2}{2b} \cdot \frac{dC}{da} = \frac{\delta^2}{2b C^2} \cdot \frac{dC}{da} = \text{const.} \cdot \frac{dC/da}{C^2} \quad (12)$$

With Eqn (11) the condition for stable crack growth becomes

$$a > L \cdot \sqrt[3]{\frac{(1 + c/L)^2}{39(c/L)^2 - 18c/L + 7}} \quad (13)$$

Hence, for the 3 cases studied ($g_{12} = 4/1$, $1/1$ and $1/4$ with $c = 107.8$ mm, 43.7 mm and 27.9 mm, respectively) the minimum crack length for stable crack growth is $a = 20.3$ mm, 27.5 mm and 32.2 mm, respectively ($L = 50$ mm).

RESULTS

Five load cases were studied: pure mode I, $g_{12} = G_I/G_{II} = \infty$, 3 Mixed-Mode I/II cases with $g_{12} = 4/1$ (80% mode I/20% mode II, corresponding to a loading position of $c = 107.8$ mm), $g_{12} = 1/1$ (50%/50%, $c = 43.7$ mm) and $g_{12} = 1/4$ (20%/80%, $c = 27.9$ mm) as well as pure mode II ($g_{12} = 0$).

In each case, 2 - 4 quasistatic tests were carried out to determine the interlaminar fracture toughness. Figure 2 shows the components of fracture G_{Ic} over G_{IIc} . The solid symbols represent the individual tests while the mean values of each case are shown as empty symbols. The fracture toughness of the thermoplastic material AS4/APC2 is significantly higher than the one of the epoxy material HTA/6376 throughout the range of load cases. AS4/APC2 exhibits only a small increase in total fracture toughness $G_{Tot,c}$ (the total SERR is the sum of the components in mode I and mode II, i.e. ordinate plus abscissa in Figure 2) as the fracture mode changes from mode I to mode II, while the mode I fracture toughness of HTA/6376 is only about 25% of the one in mode II. The reason why the fracture toughness of HTA/6376 at $g_{12} = 4/1$ (80% mode I, 20% mode II) is slightly lower than at pure mode I is not clear, however, the fracture toughness found in DCB test was $G_{Ic} = 0.36$ kJ/m², which is higher than the one specified by the manufacturer ($G_{Ic} = 0.29$ kJ/m²). The number of static tests is too small for a statistical evaluation; the emphasis of this study lay on the fatigue behaviour.

Figure 2: Components of fracture toughness G_c as function of the fracture mode

Fatigue testing was carried out in displacement control at a displacement ratio of $R = 0.1$ and a frequency of $f = 5$ Hz. During each load cycle the maximum and minimum values of displacement and load were measured and stored. The fatigue loading was interrupted periodically to measure the compliance of the system in a slow load cycle (linear regression on 2000 values of load and displacement). The analysis of the fatigue experiments is based on the compliance measurements as a function of the load cycles, $C = C(N)$. For both materials and all 5 load cases several fatigue

experiments were conducted to characterise both the initiation and growth behaviour of delaminations. However, this paper only addresses the initiation issue.

The initiation behaviour can be characterised as initiation curves $G \sim N$ in analogy to S-N curves. Crack initiation is defined as the start of delamination growth from the starter film. Since this usually happens within the specimen and hence cannot be observed visually, a suitable criterion for delamination initiation must be defined. In a planned series of Round-Robin tests the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) proposes the use of a load drop of a certain percentage (e.g. 1%) since for otherwise constant conditions a drop in the measured maximum load per cycle can only be the result of delamination growth. To avoid errors introduced by scatter or settlement effects the load measurements are approximated by a smooth curve which is then used for the 1% load drop method. This procedure has the disadvantage that depending on the fracture mode (DCB, MMB 4/1, 1/1, 1/4 or ENF) a load drop of 1% corresponds to very different increments of crack growth Δa . For typical testing parameters these increments are $\Delta a = 0.1$ mm for DCB tests, $\Delta a = 0.3$ mm for MMB test with $g_{12} = 1/1$ and $\Delta a = 0.5$ mm for ENF tests. This means that the comparability of these initiation curves is questionable. To circumvent this problem a slightly different initiation criterion is proposed in [8] that is based on a constant increment of crack growth (e.g. $\Delta a = 0.3$ mm). The load cycles to delamination initiation, N_{ini} , are determined in the following way: The increase in compliance due to a delamination extension of $\Delta a = 0.3$ mm is calculated for the actual initial crack length a_0 of the individual experiment using the relation $C \sim a^3$ for DCB test, Eqn (2) for ENF tests or Eqn (11) for MMB tests. The measured compliance values $C(N)$ are approximated by a smooth curve (e.g. a 5th order polynomial). On this curve N_{ini} is found where the increase in compliance reaches the previously determined value. If the criterion is not fulfilled after $N = 10^6$ load cycles it is assumed that delamination initiation has not occurred.

Figure 3: Delamination initiation curve, material HTA/6376, fracture mode $g_{12} = 1/4$ (20% mode I, 80% mode II)

Figure 3 shows an example of an initiation curve for Mixed-Mode loading at $g_{12} = 1/4$ (20% mode I, 80% mode II) for the epoxy material HTA/6376. For 9 fatigue experiments the total SERR, $G_{Total} = G_I + G_{II}$, calculated using Eqns (9) and (10), is plotted against the load cycles to initiation N_{ini} which were determined using the procedure outlined above. The arrow at the symbol at $N = 10^6$ indicates a run-out. At $N = 1$ the fracture toughness of the 4 quasistatic experiments is shown as well. The initiation curves for all cases under consideration (2 materials, 5 load cases) were fitted to the individual experiments (shown as solid line in Figure 3). In the region under $N = 100$ the curves are somewhat speculative due to the very limited number of experiments in that range.

Figures 4 and 5 intend to illustrate the initiation behaviour of HTA/6376 and AS4/APC2 as a function of the mode mix in the representation G_I over G_{II} as used earlier. For that purpose the intersection points of the initiation curves with the decades of the load cycle $N = 10^n$, $n = 0, 1, \dots, 6$ were taken, separated into the components G_I and G_{II} and plotted in the diagram G_I over G_{II} . The corresponding points (e.g. all 5 points for $N_{ini} = 10^3$) were connected with straight lines resulting in a graph that can be interpreted as a contour diagram. The values for $N = 10^6$ are the threshold values of the SERR, below which no crack growth occurs.

Figure 4: Delamination initiation as function of the fracture mode, material HTA/6376

Figure 5: Delamination initiation as function of the fracture mode, material AS4/APC2

It can be seen that the influence of the fracture mode decreases under fatigue loading. While the ratio of the fracture toughness in mode II and mode I is roughly $G_{IIc}/G_{Ic} \approx 4$ for HTA/6376 the threshold values G_{Thres} were found to be $G_{I, Thres} = 0.066 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ in mode I, $G_{Tot, Thres} = 0.076, 0.095$ and 0.09 kJ/m^2 in Mixed-Mode at $g_{12} = 4/1, 1/1$ and $1/4$, respectively and $G_{II, Thres} = 0.135 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ in mode II, i.e. a ratio of mode II to mode I of about 2. Rather surprising is the change in the critical fracture mode for AS4/APC2, Figure 5, where the initiation threshold values were found to be $G_{I, Thres} = 0.36 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ in mode I, $G_{Tot, Thres} = 0.27, 0.32$ and 0.17 kJ/m^2 in Mixed-Mode at $g_{12} = 4/1, 1/1$ and $1/4$, respectively and $G_{II, Thres} = 0.14 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ in mode II, i.e. the threshold in mode II is only about 40% of the one in mode I as opposed to the static case where G_{IIc} was found to be 20% larger than G_{Ic} .

A comparison of fracture toughness and threshold values yields that in mode I the threshold is about 20% of the fracture toughness for both materials, while in mode II the threshold drops to 10% and 6% for HTA/6376 and AS4/APC2, respectively. The ratios for the Mixed-Mode cases are essentially in-between these bounds except in the case $g_{12} = 1/4$ for HTA/6376 (7%).

CONCLUSIONS

A complete characterisation of the delamination behaviour of two carbon fibre reinforced plastics under the entire Mixed-Mode I/II spectrum (pure mode I, 3 cases Mixed-Mode I/II and pure mode II) in static and fatigue loading was carried out. The following results were obtained:

- The experiments under static loading confirmed the behaviour described in the literature that with increasing matrix toughness the difference in fracture toughness between mode I and mode II, G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} , decreases (HTA/6376: $G_{IIc} / G_{Ic} = 4$; AS4/APC2: $G_{IIc} / G_{Ic} = 1.2$). The reason for this behaviour is presumably that in mode II the fibres suppress the formation of a large zone of plastic deformation ahead of the crack tip and hence the increase in neat matrix toughness does not result in a similar increase in interlaminar fracture toughness of the composite. A linear Mixed-Mode fracture criterion of the form $G_I/G_{Ic} + G_{II}/G_{IIc} = 1$ seems to be adequate and conservative for both materials.
- A method to determine the delamination initiation curves was developed. The method is fairly simple and reliable and allows a direct comparison between the fracture modes. The initiation behaviour found with this method is reproducible with tolerable scatter.
- Threshold values of the strain energy release rate G_{Thres} below which no initiation of delamination growth occurs were determined for both materials and all 5 fracture modes. If the loading in a component never exceeds this threshold, delamination growth cannot occur a priori. The threshold values could be used as a design parameter in a Fail-Safe design approach.
- The characterisation of delamination growth was carried out as well but has not been addressed in this paper.

It has been confirmed that delamination in mode II becomes more and more important as the toughness of the neat matrix is improved. Moreover, under fatigue loading the mode II and Mixed-Mode cases with a large amount of mode II loading can become the critical failure modes.

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